

Challenges and Prospects of Circular Economy: Implications for National Security in Nigeria

Mathew Olusola Ebire, PhD.,¹ Tunde Omotehinse, PhD.,² & Yinka Christian Ajomale.³

¹*Global Affairs and Sustainable Development Institute (GASDI), Osun State University, Osogbo, Nigeria. Corresponding author. Email: isoleb2005@gmail.com*

²*Federal University of Agriculture, Bassambiri, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Email: Omotehinse110@gmail.com*

³*Joseph Ayo Bababola University (JABU), Ikeji-Arakeji, Osun State, Nigeria. Email: neoyinka@yahoo.com*

Abstract:

Economic security is the condition of having stable income or other resources to support a standard of living now and in the foreseeable future. Today, economic security forms, arguably, as important a part of national security. For a long time, Nigeria's economy has been linear, this means that raw materials are used to make a product, and after its use, any waste is thrown away. In an economy based on recycling, materials are reused. To ensure that in the future, there are enough raw materials for food, shelter, heating and other necessities, our economy must become circular, which means preventing waste by making products and materials more efficiently and reusing them. The paper examines the concepts of circular economy, national security, economic security - its causes and consequences. It also discusses the challenges and prospects. The paper recommends among others that Nigeria's economy be reformed in such a way that it will enable the citizens to be self-reliant; lasting employment mode should be provided by both private individuals and the three tiers of government as well as the foreign investors.

Keywords: Circular Economy, National Security, Economic Security, Challenges, Prospects, Strategies.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons

Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

1. INTRODUCTION

A circular economy, also referred to as “circularity” (Geissdoefer et al, 2020) is an economic system aimed at eliminating waste and the continual use of resources. Circular systems employ reuse, sharing, repair, refurbishment, remanufacturing and recycling to create a closed-loop system, minimizing the use of resource inputs and the creation of waste, pollution and carbon emissions (Geissdoefer et al, 2017). The circular economy aims to keep products, equipment and infrastructure (Invernizzi et al, 2020) in use for longer, thus improving the productivity of these resources. Waste materials and energy should become input for other processes: either a component or recovered resources for another industrial process or as regenerative resources for nature. This regenerative approach is in contrast to the traditional linear economy, which has a “take, make, dispose” model of production (Ellen MacArthur, 2013).

In recent years, concepts based on (re-) cycling resources are increasingly gaining importance. The most prominent among these concepts might be the circular economy, with its comprehensive support by China and the European Union. There is also a broad range of similar concepts or schools of thought, including cradle-to-cradle laws of ecology, looped and performance, regenerative design, industrial ecology, biomimicry and the blue economy (Ellen MacArthur 2012).

2. CIRCULAR ECONOMY

The circular economy is an economic concept linked to the sustainable development and the green economy but which goes further than the latter. Indeed, rather than only think to reduce the ecological impact of the industries and the amount of waste, it aims to produce goods and services by targeting a sustainable management of raw materials and energy sources (Murray, Allan et al 2015). In other words, the good is to make the economy as circular as possible by thinking to new processes and solutions for the optimization of resources and the use and waste (Kaur, Guneet et al, 2017).

However, the definition of the circular economy remains a debate in the sense that there is no official and unique definition, and therefore leaves room for multiple definitions. Nevertheless, all the definitions agree on the importance of designing, producing and consuming in a sustainable way. Its objective is to transform our society into a more circular economy compromising environmental, economic and social issues. The circular economy is based on 7 fundamental principles (Caserejos et al, 2018) which includes sustainable procurement, eco-design, industrial and territorial ecology, the economy of functionality, responsible consumption, extension of the lifespan, improvement of waste prevention management and recycling.

The idea of circular flows for materials and energy is not new, appearing as early as 1996 in the book by Kenneth E. Boulding, who explains that we should be in a “cyclical” system of production. For its part, the term “circular economy” appeared for the first time in 1988 in “*The Economics of Material Resources*” Boulding Kenneth et al in (H. Jarret 2018). This notion was developed further, following three major events: the explanation of raw materials prices between 2000 and 2010, the Chinese embargo on rare earth

materials and the arrival of economic crisis (Allwood, Julian M. 2014). Today, the climate emergency and environmental challenges have strongly influenced and pushed companies and individuals to rethink their consumption and production patterns. One of the answers to these challenges is presented by the circular economy model. Thus, new modes of production and consumption are emerging with the main objective of generating billions of dollars while controlling and reducing environmental consequences.

Circular development is directly linked to the circular economy and aims to build a sustainable society based on recycling and renewable resources, in order to protect society from waste and to be able to form a model that is no longer considering resources as infinite. This new model of economic development focuses on the production of goods and services taking into account environmental and social costs (Su Biwei, Heshmati et al, 2012). Circular development therefore supports circular economy to create new societies in line with new waste management and sustainability objectives that meet the needs of citizens. It is about enabling economies and societies, in general, to become more sustainable.

In terms of scope, the circular economy can cover a broad scope. Researchers have focused on different areas such as industrial applications with both product-oriented, natural resources and services, practice and policies (Murray Alan et al, 2015) to better understand the limitations that the circular economy currently faces, strategic management for details of the circular economy and different outcomes such as potential re-use applications (Kaur, Guneet et al, 2017) and waste management (Casarejos, Fabricio et al, 2018).

The circular economy was further modelled by British environmental economists. In *Economics of National Resources and the Environment*, they pointed out that a traditional open-ended economy was developed with no built-in tendency to recycle, which was reflected by treating the environment as a waste reservoir (Su Biwei et al, 2012).

In the early 1990s, Tim Jackson began to create the scientific basis for this new approach to industrial production in his edited collection *Clean Production Strategies*, including chapters from pre-eminent writers in the fields, such as Walter R. Stahel, Bill Rees and Robert Coustanza. At the time still called 'preventive environmental management', his follow-on book *Material Concerns: Pollution, Profit and Quality of Life*, Tim Jackson synthesized these findings into a manifesto for change, moving industrial production away from an extractive linear system towards a more circular economy (Su Biwei et al, 2012).

Promoting a circular economy was identified as national policy in China's 11th five-year plan starting in 2016 (Ellen MacArthur 2013). The Ellen MacArthur foundation has more recently outlined the economic opportunity of a circular economy, bringing together complementary schools of thought in an attempt to create a coherent framework, thus giving the concept a wide exposure and appeal (Ellen MacArthur 2013).

Circular economy often refers to quantities of recycled materials or reduced waste, however Cradle to Cradle Design focuses on quality of products including safety for humans and environmental health. Popularized by the book *Cradle to Cradle: Remaking the way we make things*, Cradle to Cradle Design has been widely implemented by Architect Williams McDonough, who was introduced as the “father of the circular economy” while receiving the 2017 Fortune Award for Circular Economy Leadership in Davos during the World Economic Forum (Kristoffersen Eivind et al, 2020). Korhonen Nuur, Feldmann and Birkie (2018) opine that definitions of circular economy that focus on system change often emphasize the following three elements:

- 3 Closed cycles
- 4 Renewable energy
- 5 Systems thinking

Some researchers argue that social inclusiveness is also a necessary part of the circular economy (Korhonen et al, 2018).

1. Closed cycles

In a circular economy, material cycles are closed following the example of an ecosystem. There is no such thing as waste, because every residual stream can be used to make a new product. Toxic substances are eliminated and residual flows are separated into a biological and a technical circle. Producers take back their products after use and repair them for a new useful life (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015). In this system, it is therefore not only important that materials are received properly, but also that products, components and raw materials remain of high quality in these circles (Korhonen, Nuur, Feldman Birkie, 2018).

2. Renewable Energy

Just like raw materials and products, energy also lasts as long as possible in a circular economy. The circular economic system is fed by renewable energy sources. Because it is not possible to recycle energy, there is no mention of energy cycles but of ‘Cascade type energy flows’ (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015). An example of this is the co-production of heat and power.

3. Systems Thinking

The circular economy does not only require closed material cycles and renewable energy, but also systems thinking. Every actor in the economy (company, person, organism) is connected to other actors. Together, this forms a network in the actions of one player influence other players. To take this into account, the short and long-term consequences must be taken into account in chokes, as well as the impact of the entire value chain (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015).

3. CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND NET POSITIVITY

In the face of rising populations and resources demand, circular economy finds its origins from the attempt of countries of the global north to respond to the current unsustainable approaches to production, consumption and disposal of materials. The linear economic system is an approach that translates to unprecedented consumption, waste generation and heightened stress on natural systems. A circular economy on the other hand drives to close loops by maximizing the utility and useful lifespan of materials. The circular economy as a foundation for systems – driven economic development will mean that materials will be used and reused for longer durations.

The Ethical Circular Economy (ECE) is an effort to remedy the discrepancy between Circular Economy as a resource effectiveness and efficiency framework, and the current lack of widespread social equity and access around the world, specifically in developing countries (Olufemi and Obafemi, 2016).

The world's first Ethical Circular Economy workshop held in Lagos, April 2016 reports that “with the annual profits of many multinational companies outranking the GDPs of many nation states, it is becoming increasingly palpable that the Governments of the world no longer “govern” in the traditional sense of the word. ‘The Forum for the Future’, the World Wildlife Fund’ and ‘The Climate Group’ have recently formulated a new concept that provides the best chance for common wellbeing”. This new framework is called Net-Positive. The Net-Positive encourages multi-national corporations, local businesses and individuals to behave, buy, collaborate and make business decisions that can ideally be “good” – inventing back into society and the environment, and “giving in” than they “take out”.

4. NATIONAL SECURITY

Security can be described as the back bone of any society. It is tied to its social, political, economic and cultural growth. Negligence of this vital ingredient of development has led to all manner of social ills, including violent crimes such as armed robbery, ritual killings, child trafficking and other crimes (Maryam, 2010). The fact remains that without security, there cannot be meaningful development. There is no doubt that security is an enabler of national development. Balogun, (2012) also agreed to the fact that peace and security is an essential factor of human life. He stressed that a peaceful and secured environment is central to every country since it affects all aspects of economic and social development in a country.

National security is the safety of a nation against threats such as terrorism, war, kidnapping, inter-communal clashes, inter-tribal clashes, armed bandits, herdsmen and farmers' clashes. According to Joshua, Ibietan and Azuh (2016), national security is the safekeeping of the nation as a whole. Its highest business is the protection of the nation as a whole and its people from attack and other external dangers by maintaining armed force and guarding of the state secrets. National security as defined by Obi (2015) refers to the protection of the nation from attack or other danger by holding adequate armed forces and guarding state secrets. It should be noted however that national security should

not be narrowed down to defense and military might alone. It is wider than that. It is this narrow conception of national security that forms the basis for the disproportionate budgetary allocation of the funds as the case is, to ensure the security of lives and property, however, to the utter neglect of other equally important sectors of the economy that bear directly or indirectly on national security. Such sectors as education, health, and agriculture, which have become poorly mobilized (Ishaq, Musa and Abdulhafiz 2019).

Sheidu (2014) in an attempt to give national security wider narration, defined it as the ability of a state to overcome any form of its challenges no matter what the challenges is. He asserted that national security is wider than military might, defense or law enforcement and pointed out other rather basic dimensions like job, water, and food security. Elechi (2018) declared that the recent international debates have revised the need to see national security in the broader sense as the struggle to secure the most basic necessities of life such as food, fuel, medicine and shelter. The broader view of national security from the perspective of human psychological and national security and overall peace and development, as social interest arising from the absence of such basic human needs can lead to security problems and conflicts. Based on the broader view of national security, one therefore define national security as the efforts of the government in ensuring that a nation is free from external attacks and internal violence of any kinds so that the nation could be peaceful in such a manner that the citizens and foreigners would be free to carry out their legitimate activities that will enhance their individual development and that of the nation at large. It is appropriate to state that a national security policy would be of no use to the unemployed and hungry citizens in a country like ours.

National security is a top public issue today in Nigeria. It is a matter of national importance that should be of concern to all stakeholders. Nigeria is today plagued with social disorder, terrorism, unemployment, inter-tribal clashes, inter-communal clashes, illiteracy, herdsmen and farmer clashes, poverty, religious conflicts, kidnapping, armed bandits, corruption, political crises, and armed robbery. All these according to Balogun (2021) imply that we are insecure in terms of human wellbeing.

These problems, individually and collectively constitute threats to the peace, security and development of Nigeria. These security challenges are diverse and complex in nature with alarming dimensions and consequences. Balogun (2021) identified 11 courses of insecurity in Nigeria to include:

- 2 Religious and ethnic difference.
- 3 Unemployment and poverty.
- 4 Illiteracy and ignorance.
- 5 Financial attachment to political positions or offices.
- 6 Inequality in sharing of national resources and political office holders.
- 7 Depreciating value system.
- 8 Corruption.

- 9 Poor governance.
- 10 Weak judicial system.
- 11 Open borders.
- 12 Weak security system.

The security crises in different parts of Nigeria is destroying existing infrastructure and preventing a peaceful environment for the development of further infrastructure, and a safe environment for economic activities by individuals. No nation can achieve sustainable development in an environment of insecurity (Balogun 2021).

Balogun (2021) also identified consequences of insecurity to Nigeria as follows:

- I. Social dislocation and displacement of people.
- II. Dislocation and disruption of family and community life.
- III. General atmosphere of mistrust, fear, anxiety and frenzy.
- IV. Deepening of hungers, poverty among the people due to increase rate of unemployment since foreign investors are not willing to come into the country.
- V. Atmosphere of political insecurity and instability including declining confidence in the political leadership and apprehension about the system.
- VI. Government deficit as a result of huge expenses on security personnel and equipment as well as resettlement of the displaced people and fixing of the destroyed infrastructures.
- VII. Inhuman treatment of people especially in areas where rape, child abuse and neglect are used as instruments of war.
- VIII. Heightened hostility between 'indigenes' and the 'settlers'.
- IX. Politicians and other government officials hide under the insecurity situation to either kill, harass or intimidate their political opponents or enemies and steal government money.
- X. Loss of vibrant citizens through kidnapping, abduction and killing while others have been lured into terrorist organization.

5. INTERFACE BETWEEN ECONOMIC SECURITY AND NATIONAL SECURITY

Economic security or financial security is the condition of having stable income or other resources to support a standard of living now and in the foreseeable future and it has also been proposed as a key determinant of international relations, particularly in the geopolitics of petroleum in American foreign policy after September 11, 2001. This tilts towards sustainable development (Balogun, 2021). Going further, Balogun accepts that Economic Security includes:

- (a) Probable continual solvency.
- (b) Predictability of the future cash flow of a person or other economic entity, such as a country.

(c) Employment security or job security.

Financial security more often refers to individual and family money management and savings (*Financial Security in Later Life 2011*). Economic security tends to include the broader effect of a society's production levels and monetary support for non-working citizens.

In the United States, children's economic security is indicated by the income level and employment security of their families and organizations (*Key National Indicators of Well-Being 2007*). Economic security of people over 50 years old is based on social security benefits, pensions and savings, earnings and employment, and health insurance coverage.

Economic security in the content of politics and international relations, is the ability of a nation-state to follow its choice of policies to develop the national economy in the manner desired. Historically, conquests of nations have made conquerors rich through plunder, access to new resources and enlarged trade through controlling of the conquered nations' economy. In today's complex system of international trade, characterized by multi-national agreements, mutual inter-dependence and availability of natural resources et cetera, economic security today forms, arguably, as important a part of national security as military policy, moreso, with co-habitation of people from different ethnic, religious, economic and cultural backgrounds and other forms of identities (Joshua et al, 2016).

In Canada, threats to the country's overall economic security are considered economic espionage, which is "illegal, clandestine or coercive activity" by a foreign government in order to gain unauthorized access to economic intelligence, such as proprietary information or technology, for economic advantage. It is, of course believed that there is a tradeoff between economic security and economic opportunity (Hellen MacArthur, 2015).

Also, the interconnections between national security and the economy of countries have grown as globalization and economic integration have increased over decades. In the globally interconnected and interdependence world, the economy is intimately connected with both national and international security: economic security is an important component of national security. The economy influences national security by shaping the functioning of the society internally, as well as by influencing the broader geopolitical place of a country internationally (Hellen MacArthur, 2015).

6. CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY

6.1 Challenges

There is some criticism of the idea of the circular economy. As Corvellec (2015) put it, the circular economy privileges continued economic growth with soft "anti-programs" and the circular economy is far from the most radical "anti-programs". Corvellec (2019) raised the issue of multi-species and stresses "impossibility for waste producers to dissociate

themselves from their waste and emphasizes the contingent, multiple, and transient value of waste.

Scatolic engagement draws on Reno's analogy of waste as scats and of scats as signs for enabling interspecies communication. This analogy stresses again, the impossibility for waste producers to dissociate themselves from their waste and emphasizes the contingent, multiple, and transient value of waste (Corvellec and Stal, 2019). According to Corvellec, a key tenet of a scatolic approach to waste is to consider waste as unavoidable and worthy of interest. Whereas total quality sees in waste, a sign of failure, a scatolic understanding sees a sign of life. Likewise, whereas the circular Economy analogy of a circle evokes endless perfection, the analogy of scats evokes disorienting messiness. A scatolic approach features waste as a lively matter open for interpretation, within organizations as well as across organizational species (Corvellec 2019).

Also, Corvellec and Stal (2019) are mildly critical of apparel manufacturing circular economy take-back systems as ways to anticipate and head off more severe waste reduction programs. Apparel retailers exploit that the circular economy is evocative but still sufficiently vague to create any concrete policies that might hinder their freedom of action (Corvellec & Stal, 2019). Research by Zink and Geyer (2017) questioned the circular economy's engineering-centric assumptions. "However, proponents of the circular economy have tended to look at the world purely as an engineering system and have overlooked the economic part of the circular economy. Recent research has started to question the core of the circular economy – namely, whether closing material and product loops do, in fact prevent primary production (Zink and Geyer 2017).

Alwood (2014) discussed the limits of circular Economy 'material circularity', and questioned the desirability of the Circular Economy in a reality with growing demand. Do Circular Economy secondary production activities (reuse, repair, and remake) actually reduce, or instead displace, primary production (natural resource extraction)? The problem Circular Economy overlooks, its untold story, is how displacement is governed mainly by market forces, according to McMillan et al (2012). It is the tired old narrative, that the invisible hand of market forces will conspire to create full displacement of virgin material of the same kind (Zink and Geyer 2017).

6.2 Prospects

The circular economy as a new way of creating value and ultimately prosperity, works by extending product lifespan through improved design and servicing, and relocating waste from the end of the supply chain to the beginning – in effect, using resources more efficiently by using them over and over, not only once; one in which industry adopts the reuse and service-life extension of goods as a strategy of waste prevention, regional job creation, and resource efficiency in order to decouple wealth from resource consumption (Ellen MacArthur 2017).

Governments are also encouraging – and, in some cases, requiring the adoption of circular economy principles and practices that would lead to more resource efficiency and

less waste. Even, at the global level, the Sustainable Development Goals, adopted by the United Nations Member States in 2015 include many related ambitions.

There are also efficiency gains. According to the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, by 2021 about \$ 1 trillion per year of materials cost savings could be generated from circular business models. National economies, entrepreneurs and employees will benefit, as they form new businesses and create new jobs to fill niches created by the circular economy, through resource recovery and remanufacturing.

Developing countries stand to also profit immensely from a circular economy. There is a growing need for materials, water and energy because of both population growth and increased demand by infrastructure, industry and consumers in developing countries, so, circular economy activities have the potential to address a significant share of this need – dampening or possibly reversing the rise in resource use by developing countries, and in term reducing resource depletion, climate change and the pollution of natural areas. In fact, a report from the Mckinsey Global Institute estimates that up to 85 percent of opportunities to improve resource productivity lie in developing countries (Ellen MacArthur 2017).

7. CONCLUSION

The world population is undoubtedly increasing and it is affecting the environment. There is thus the desire for enough food, water and prosperity in 2050 and expectedly, beyond, to guarantee Economic and National Security of Nations, mostly, developing countries and particularly, the Nigerian State. There is undoubtedly gross insecurity of lives, properties and businesses across the entire landscape of Nigeria. This begs for serious intervention. Insecurity and impropriety in economic planning would continuously be impactful on Nigeria's Economic Security. Also, prospects of a circular economy have been found to be more prosperous and sustainable than a linear economy. In a circular economy, we treat our environment responsibly because raw materials are obtained in such a manner that natural and human environment are not damaged, unlike a linear economy in which waste derived from raw materials used are thrown away.

7.1 Recommendations

Nigeria's economy needs to switch from a linear to a circular economy. The circular economy does not aim at changing the profit maximization paradigm of business. Rather, it suggests an alternative way of thinking how to attain a sustained competitive advantage, while concurrently addressing the environmental and socio-economic concerns. Stepping away from linear forms of production most often leads to the development of new core competencies along the value chain and ultimately superior performance that cuts cost, improves efficiency, meets advanced government regulations and the expectations of green consumers.

To ensure healthy and safe living and working conditions, and cause less harm to the environment, Nigeria's economy must be 'green', devoid of both National Insecurity and economic dislocations. This means that the Nigerian government must facilitate the

assemblage of experts who will engender a result-oriented and workable security and economic policies, that would translate into long lasting and enduring economic security.

Within the content of a developing economy like Nigeria, the key aim should be to achieve robust economic growth and provide opportunity for all social groups, while simultaneously improving environmental quality and eradicating all forms of insecurity. The Nigerian government should reform its economy in such a way that it will enable the citizens to be self-reliant while employment mode should be provided by both private individuals and the three tiers of government as well as the foreign investors.

Families should be encouraged to properly bring-up their children by inculcating the right type of values in the children which will guide them from being thrown into any kinds of crimes. Government should adopt economic policies or programmes that will attract foreign investors so as to increase job availability that will help to reduce unemployment.

People of impeccable characters with high level of intelligence should be the focus in the recruitment of Security Personnel in Nigeria while they should as well be equipped, with their welfare being of paramount concern to the government. Finally, all Nigeria's borders should be appropriately guarded and effectively monitored to prevent influx and unfavourable movements of foreigners, from neighbouring countries, under the guise of unwarranted transborder trade relations.

References

- Alwood, Julian M. (2014). "Squaring the Circular Economy. The role of recycling within a hierarchy of material management strategies" *In Handbook of recycling state-of-the-art for practitioner, analyst and scientists, edited E. Worrel and M. Reuter Waltham, MA, USA Elsevier.*
- Balogun B.N. (2012). Understanding Causes and Consequences of National Insecurity in Nigeria: Education as Panacea. *International Journal of Multi-Disciplinary in Educational Research and Development 2 (4), 137-152.*
- Boulding, Kenneth E. (2018). In H. Jarret (ed). Environmental Quality in a Growing Economy, Resources for the Future. *John Hopkins University Press, Baltimore, MD.*
- Casarejos, Fabricio, Claudio, R., Rufin, Carlos, Frota, Mauricio N. (2018). "Rethinking packaging production and consumption vis-a-vis circular economy. A case study of compostable cassava starch-based material". *Journal of Cleaner Production. 201.*
- Corvellec, Herve. (2015). "New directions for management and organization studies on waste". Technical report. Gothenburg Research Institute. University of Gothenburg.
- Corvellec, Herve. (2019). "Waste as Scats for Organizational engagement with waste". *Organization 26 (2).*
- Corvellec, H & Stal, H.I. (2019). "Qualification as Corporate activism: How Swedish apparel retailers attach circular fashion qualities to take-back systems". *Scandinavian Journal of Management, 35 (3).*
- Elechi, C.N (2018). Managing education for national security. A case for utilitarian education. *International Journal of creative minds and productivity, 1(1), 1-9.*
- Ellen MacArthur (2013). Towards the Circular Economy. Economic and Business Rationale for an Accelerated Transition. Ellen MacArthur Foundation.
- Geissdoerfer, M., Pieroni, M.P., Pigosso, D.C and Soufani, K. (2020). "Circular business models: A review". *Journal of Cleaner Production. 277.*
- Geissdoerfer, Martin, Savaget, Paulo Bocken Nancy M.P., Hullink, Erik Jan (2017). "The Circular Economy – A new sustainability Paradigm?". *Journal of Cleaner Production. 143.*
- Invernizzi, Diletta Collette., Locatelli, Giorgio., Valentoorf, Anne; Love, Peter ED;
- Pumell, Phil Brookes, Naomi, J. (2020). "Developing policies for the end-of-life of energy infrastructure. Coming to terms with the challenges of decommissioning". *Energy Policy. 144.*
- Ishaq, A.B., Musa, A., & Abdulhafiz, Z. (2019). Education and insecurity. Retrieved from www.researchgate.net.
- Jackson, Tim (1996). Material Concern Pollution, Profit and Quality of Life. Routledge.

- Joshua, S., Ibietan, J., & Azuh, D. (2016). Education and Nigeria's national security. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 2 (8), 3660-3665.
- Kaur Gunnet., Uisan, Kristiadi., Lun Ong; Khali, Sze Ki Lin, Carol (2017). "Recent trend in Green sustainable chemistry and waste valorization: Rethinking plastics in a circular economy." *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry*. 9.
- Korhonen, J., Nuur, C., Feldmann, A., & Birkie, S.E (2018). Circular economy as an essentially contested concept". *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 175.
- Kristoffersen, Eivind; Blomsma, Fenna; Mikalef Patrick; Li Jingyue (2020). "The smart circular economy. A digital – enabled circular strategies framework for manufacturing companies. *Journal of Business Research*. 120.
- Maryam, G. (2010). Nigeria Security and National Development. www.dailytrust.com
- McMillian, C. A., S. J. Skerlos, and G.A Keoleian (2012). "Evaluation of the metals industry's position on recycling and its implications for environmental emissions". *Journal of Industrial Ecology*. 16 (3).
- Murray, Alan., Skene, Keith., Haynes, Kathryn (2015). "The Circular Economy: An Interdisciplinary Exploration of the Concept and Application in a Global Context". *Journal of Business Ethics*. 140.
- Obi, C. (2015) Challenges of insecurity and terrorism in Nigeria: Implication for national development. *Conference Journal of Education*, 1 (1)
- Olufemi, O, and Obafemi, A. (2016). Implementing an Ethical Circular Economy in Lagos, Nigeria. World's First Ethical Circular Economy Workshop held in Lagos, April 2016. *Joint report of The Sustainability School, Lagos and The New Nigeria Foundation, Lagos*.
- Su. Biwei., Heshmati, Alimas., Geng, Yong., Yu. Xiaoman (2012). "A review of the circular economy in China; moving from rhetoric to implementation". *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 42.
- Valenzuela, F., & Bohun, S. (2017). "Against wasted politics: A critique of the circular economy". *Ephemera theory & politics in organization*. 17
- Zink, T. & Geyer, R. (2017). "Circular economy rebound". *Journal of Industrial Ecology*. 21.